

Diverse approaches to manage early excess reactivity of VVER 1200 reactor

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to manage the initial excess reactivity of the VVER-1200 reactor through different approaches, including the use of burnable absorbers and control rods in fuel assemblies with varying enrichments (from 4.95 wt.% to 2.0 wt.%) by using the Monte Carlo code Serpent. It is found that 30 integrated burnable absorbers (IBAs) rods are required to reduce the infinite multiplication factor (k_{inf}) from 1.32408 to 1.06983 in assemblies containing 4.95 wt.% enriched fuel. On the other hand, assemblies with enrichment below 2.5 wt.% do not require any IBA rods. Control rods (CRs) can also effectively reduce excess reactivity at the beginning of life (BOL), provided they are inserted more than 80% of the assembly's height. When fully inserted, the CRs provide a reactivity worth of 85.5 pcm/cm in 4.95 wt.% enriched assemblies at BOL. Fuel enrichment has a significant impact on delayed neutron fraction as well as the FTC, and MTC. While the effect of IBA rods on these parameters is found to be insignificant; however they do harden the neutron spectrum at the BOL due to the thermal neutron absorption by isotopes ¹⁵⁵Gd and ¹⁵⁷Gd.

Keywords

VVER-1200, Excess Reactivity, burnable absorbers, IBA Rod, Control Rod, Enrichment, Delayed Neutron, FTC, MTC

Introduction

Higher reactivity value is required to balance burnup and the accumulation of fission product poisons during the operation of a reactor. But large excess reactivity is undesirable because they requisite a large amounts of neutron poisons to be present in the core to compensate for them (Souza and Mesquita 2011; Khrais et al. 2019; Evans et al. 2022). In practical case, the excess reactivity existing in a freshly loaded reactor is balanced by the position of shim and control rods (CRs), by adding boron to the reactor coolant, or introducing integral burnable fuel absorber (Shelley et al. 2000; Mart et al. 2014; Ishraq et al. 2024a). Gadolinia (Gd_2O_3) which is a very commonly

used burnable absorber, mixed with UO_2 as integrated burnable absorbers (IBAs), used in some fuel rods of an assembly (Ovi et al. 2021; Shelley and Ovi 2021). These burnable absorbers, upon neutron absorption, undergo transformation into materials with reduced neutron absorption cross sections, thereby enabling prolonged control over neutron multiplication within the reactor system (Amaya et al. 2002; Mart et al. 2014; Galahom 2016; Ovi et al. 2021). These burnable absorbers aid in providing a uniform flux distribution across a core by suppressing excess initial reactivity due to their high absorption cross section (Choe et al. 2016). This not only flattens the power distribution for longer period and avoids high power peaks of fresh fuel assemblies, but also reduces the

possibility of positive moderator temperature coefficient (MTC) and the reliance on complicated control mechanisms using dedicated poison rods (Reda et al. 2020; Shelley and Ovi 2022). But the increased use of IBA can cause shorter cycle length due to reduction in fissile content loading along with difficulties in peak power control (Tran et al. 2019; Mohsen et al. 2022). Hence, the optimization of IBA rods for different enriched assemblies in managing excess reactivity is required.

Several innovative burnable absorber (BA) techniques that have been proposed in recent years to improve reactivity control and optimize fuel utilization. One such advancement is the use of coated burnable absorbers, where materials like Gd_2O_3 or B_4C are applied as thin layers on fuel pellets or particles (Raju et al. 2023). This configuration provides a more uniform neutron absorption profile and minimizes the impact on fuel matrix integrity. Studies have demonstrated that this technique can enhance reactivity suppression during the early stages of burnup while reducing local burnup penalties (Wu et al. 2019). Building on this approach, double-coated BA particles have been introduced, consisting of an absorber core surrounded by two separate layers—typically ceramic or refractory coatings such as SiC or ZrO_2 . These additional coatings help improve mechanical stability, reduce chemical reactivity with the fuel, and provide better shielding from high neutron flux, making them suitable for high-burnup or high-temperature environments (Zhang et al. 2021). Researcher (Ishraq et al. 2025) investigated the thermal performance of coated IBAs under SMR conditions, emphasizing their compatibility with passive safety systems, while (Jo and Shin 2022) explored concentric BA arrangements to optimize self-shielding effects.

Our greater interest on VVER-1200 reactor, which is currently under construction and will be commissioned soon in our country as Rooppur Nuclear Power Plant (RNPP) (Shelley et al. 2022, 2024; Sharmin et al. 2023). Researcher around the world are doing research to improve and understanding the neutronic behaviour of VVER reactors. The possibility for large-scale production of ^{238}Pu in the core of a VVER-1000 power reactor is studied by (Shmelev et al. 2023); MOX fuel is used in VVER-1200 reactor to achieve a higher burnup by (Ozoani and Volkov 2023); neutronic characteristics during the fuel burnup process with and without fuel cooling are compared by (Lavronenko et al. 2022); effective algorithm is used to minimize the amount of liquid radioactive wastes during water exchange in the primary circuit of a nuclear power plant by (Soloviev et al. 2022). As we know, VVER-1200 reactor utilizes different enriched assembly (from 4.95 wt.% to 1.6 wt.%) in the core to flatten the power distribution (Kotov et al. 2021). Managing the early excess reactivity and ensuring flat power distribution along with other safety parameters for each different enriched assembly of the core is mandatory to avoid any anomaly like fuel melt, and non-uniform power etc. For these reasons, we are going to undertake a study that aims to optimize the number and appropriate position of IBA rods for dif-

ferent enriched assemblies. From this study, it is expected that we will be able to figure out the different way of managing early excess reactivity without compromising any safety parameters. For practical utilization of our study, we will analyse safety parameters such as fuel and moderator temperature coefficient, delayed neutron fraction along with other neutronic behaviour. It is expected that this study will put a contribution to the enhancement of design as well as analysis of the VVER-1200 assembly.

Materials and methods

The VVER-1200/AES-2006 reactor is a pressurized water moderated reactor (PWR) that consists of 163 fuel assemblies, each of which consists of 331 rods in total, with 312 fuel rods, 18 guide tubes and 1 instrumentation tube. Radial view of the reference VVER-1200 assembly (modelled by Serpent 2.1.32) has been shown in Fig. 1. The detailed neutronic calculations were done using Serpent 2.1.32 (Leppänen et al. 2015) and ENDF/B-VII.0 nuclear data library (Smith 2011). Serpent is a Monte Carlo reactor physics simulation software, developed by the VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland. Each simulation tracked the history of 20,000 particles across 1000 cycles or batches, with the first 100 cycles skipped to ensure source convergence. A high accuracy of the results was achieved, with a standard deviation of approximately 0.01% in the k_{inf} . Chemical shim in the form of soluble boron or solbor (boric acid, enriched to 19.9 wt.% ^{10}B) was employed, with a boron concentration of 600 ppm (Shelley et al. 2025). Burnup step is considered, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, and 60 GWd/t. The effective delayed neutron fraction (β_{eff}) was determined in Serpent using Meulekamp's method (Meulekamp and Marck 2006). The design parameters considered for modelling the reference VVER-1200 assembly are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Design parameters considered for the reference VVER-1200 assembly

Parameters	Values
Fuel pellet hole radius	0.60 mm
Fuel pellet outer radius	3.80 mm
Clad thickness	0.685 mm
Pin pitch	12.75 mm
Assembly Power	19.63 MW _{th}
Reactor Power	3200 MW _{th}
Fuel assembly pitch	23.60 cm
Active fuel height	375 cm
Fuel temperature	873.0 K
Non-fuel temperature	573.0 K
Density of UO_2	10.97 g/cm ³
Density of Gd_2O_3	7.41 g/cm ³
Moderator	Light water
Boron concentration in moderator	600 ppm

Figure 1. (a) Fuel cell, (b) Radial view of VVER-1200 reactor Assembly.

The fuel density of 10.97 g/cm^3 as mentioned in Table 1, refers to the theoretical density (TD) of UO_2 . The actual density of fuel used in the simulations is 10.42 g/cm^3 , which corresponds to 95% of TD (Ishraq et al. 2024b). The Fuel Temperature Coefficient (FTC) and Moderator Temperature Coefficient (MTC) were calculated by using a specified methodology. The process began by determining the infinite multiplication factor (k_{inf}) at a reference average fuel temperature of 873 K and a moderator temperature of 573 K. Subsequently, material depletion was simulated for various burnup steps using the command 'set printm 1'. To calculate the temperature coefficients, separate perturbations were introduced at burnup steps of 0, 20, and 60 MWd/kg. Specifically, the fuel temperature was increased by 300 K, and the moderator temperature was independently increased by 30 K, with corresponding changes in moderator density being considered to calculate k_{inf} .

The following formulas were used to find FTC and MTC (Burns et al. 2020; Ishraq et al. 2024c).

$$\text{FTC} = \frac{k(T_{\text{Fuel}}) - k}{k \times 300} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{MTC} = \frac{k(T_{\text{Moderator}}) - k}{k \times 30} \quad (2)$$

Here, k denotes the infinite multiplication factor at the initial fuel/moderator temperature, $k(T)$ is the multiplication factor at the perturbed temperature of the fuel/moderator.

Results and discussion

Effect of enrichment on infinite multiplication factor (k_{inf})

Fig. 2 shows the variation of the infinite multiplication factor (k_{inf}) with burnup for different enriched (from 4.95 wt.% to 2.0 wt.%) UO_2 fuelled assemblies, without the introduction of any burnable absorbers or CR insertions. As expected, both k_{inf} and early excess reactivity show higher values in high enriched assemblies, which are necessary to decrease for the safe and stable operation of the reactor. A sharp drop in k_{inf}

occurs during the first 20 effective full power days (EFPDs), mainly due to the buildup of fission product poisons—especially ^{135}Xe . This isotope is produced both directly from fission and indirectly from the decay of another fission product, ^{135}I . Because ^{135}Xe is a very strong neutron absorber, with a high thermal neutron absorption cross-section ($\sim 2.7 \times 10^6$ barns), its increasing concentration causes a temporary dip in reactor reactivity. After that, the k_{inf} decreases almost linearly with burnup in higher enriched assemblies, but flattens out at around 40 GWd/t burnup in lower enriched assemblies. It is expected that the production of secondary fissile Pu-239 from U-238 is higher in low enriched assemblies and does not allow falling the k_{inf} further with burnup.

Figure 2. Effect of varying enrichments on k_{inf} with burnup.

Manage of early excess reactivity

Orientation of integrated burnable absorber (IBA) rods

Integrated burnable absorber (IBA) rods are the homogeneous mixture of fuel and neutron absorbers. This research encompasses the exploration of distinct configurations of IBA rods within the assembly, comprising a total of 312 fuel rods. The number of IBA rods considered in this study is 8, 12, 18, 24, and 30, allowing for an assessment of the impact of these specific quantities on

Figure 3. Position of the (a) 30, (b) 24, (c) 18, and (d) 12 IBA rods in the fuel assembly (modelled by Serpent 2.1.32 code).

the overall system performance. The positions of the IBA in the fuel assembly have been illustrated in Fig. 3. In this study, 4 wt.% gadolinium (III) oxide (Gd_2O_3) is used as a neutron absorber with UO_2 fuel.

Fig. 4 shows the variation of k_{inf} with burnup for different numbers of IBA rods in assemblies with enrichments from 2.0 wt.% to 4.95 wt.%. Fig. 4a shows that the largest numbers of IBA rods are needed to be used in the assembly (utilizing 4.95 wt.% enrichment) to suppress the large early excess reactivity. Considering the standard early excess reactivity of 5 ~ 10% or k_{inf} of 1.05 ~ 1.1, it can be observed that for 4.95 wt.% enrichment, use of 30 IBA rods is suitable. It reduced the value of k_{inf} from 1.32408 to 1.06983 at BOL. Adding more IBA rods will lead to more thermal neutrons' absorption by Gd-155 and Gd-157 atoms and take the k_{inf} below 1.05 as shown in Fig. 4a. Gd-155 and Gd-157 have exceptionally high absorption cross-sections (60,737 barns and 252,912 barns respectively at thermal neutron energies), which makes them highly effective in suppressing excess reactivity (Razu et al. 2023). By a similar analysis, for 4.5, 4.0, 3.5, 3.0, 2.5 wt.% enrichments, the optimum number of IBA rods are determined to be 24, 18, 18, 12 and 8 respectively. For 2.0 wt.% enrichment, the best results are obtained for the total elimination of all IBA rods. After 10 GWd/t burnup, the effect of burnable absorber in the IBAs rods are disappear for all the cases as demonstrated in Fig. 2.

Effect of IBA rods and enrichment on neutron spectrum

Fig. 5a demonstrates the effect of IBA on the spectrum at BOL and end EOL for 4.95 wt.% enriched fuel. The presence of burnable absorbers significantly influences the neutron spectrum at the BOL. IBAs are poisons intentionally introduced to control the reactivity and prolong the fuel cycle/life. These absorbers preferentially absorb neutrons, particularly in the thermal energy region. As a result, the total number of thermal neutrons in thermal region gets reduced and the average energy shifts towards higher value. Consequently, introduction of IBAs make the neutron spectrum harder at BOL. Fig. 5a also confirms that there are no significant changes of neutron spectrum at EOL as ^{155}Gd and ^{157}Gd atoms sustain up to 10 GWd/t but not up to EOL. Hence, there is no question of impact of IBA on neutron spectrum at EOL. Fig. 5b demonstrates the effect of fuel enrichment on neutron spectrum. The enrichment level of the fuel affects the neutron spectrum, especially in the thermal energy zone. Higher enriched fuel assemblies exhibit a harder neutron spectrum in the thermal region due to increased fission reactions and a larger population of higher-energy neutrons at BOL. At EOL, the effect of fissile Pu such as Pu-239 is significant. As assemblies with lower enrichment produce more Pu-239 at EOL, they have harder spectrum in the thermal energy region, which is reverse of BOL. Therefore, at EOL, the effect of enrichment on the spectrum is opposite of BOL. This variation in the neutron spectrum affects the reactivity, fuel utilization, and performance of the reactor.

Figure 4. Effect of IBA rods on the k_{∞} of different enriched VVER-1200 assemblies. (a) 4.95 wt.%, (b) 4.5 wt.%, (c) 4.0 wt.%, (d) 3.5 wt.%, (e) 3.0 wt.%, (f) 2.5 wt.%, and (g) 2.0 wt.%.

Figure 5. Effect of (a) IBA and (b) fuel enrichment on the neutron spectrum.

Effect of control rod (CR) insertion on reactivity

Fig. 6 shows the effect of CRs insertion on the k_{inf} , both with and without IBA rods. The CRs are made from B_4C , which contains natural boron (19.9% B-10 and 80.1% B-11). Natural boron consisting of B-10 (19.9%) and B-11 (80.1%) isotopes is used in the form of B_4C to fabricate the CRs. For this analysis, a 4.95 wt.% enriched UO_2 fuel assembly was used as the reference case. Each assembly contains 18 CRs and they are inserted through the guide tubes, which are shown in Fig. 1b The CRs are inserted from the bottom up to the full height of the assembly. Each assembly includes 18 control rods inserted through guide tubes). The CRs are inserted from the bottom up to the full height of the assembly.

Fig. 6a shows that inserting CRs to more than 80% of the assembly height is effective in reducing the early

excess reactivity. However, the withdrawal of CRs by 25 cm from full insertion increases the reactivity by more than 15% at BOL. Fig. 6b illustrates the combined effect of CRs and IBA rods on k_{inf} . When both are used together, early excess reactivity can be effectively controlled at any insertion height.

Fig. 7 illustrates the variation of CRs worth over time for a certain position during the burnup both with and without IBA rods. The analysis was done using a 4.95 wt.% enriched fuel assembly, with CRs inserted to heights of 25 cm, 75 cm, 125 cm, and 175 cm throughout the burnup process. The calculated results indicate a linear decrease in the CR worth as the burnup progresses because of the production of neutron poison, and activation of CR material. At the beginning of life (BOL), the CR worths are 7.2, 32.7, and 85.5 pcm/cm for insertion heights of 25, 75, and 125 cm,

Figure 6. Effect of CR insertion on k_{inf} with and without IBA.

Figure 7. Change of CR worth with burnup (a) without and (b) with IBA rods.

respectively. By the end of life (EOL), these values drop to 4.9, 23.1, and 57.4 pcm/cm. Fig. 7b suggests that CR worth is lower when IBA rods are used in the assembly. This happens because ¹⁵⁵Gd and ¹⁵⁷Gd in the IBA rods absorb some of the thermal neutrons, reducing the effectiveness of the control rods. While B-10 in the CRs has a high thermal neutron absorption cross-section (about 3848 barns), it is still lower than that of ¹⁵⁵Gd and ¹⁵⁷Gd, which makes gadolinium more effective at absorbing thermal neutrons.

Safety parameters

Effective delayed neutron fraction (β_{eff})

The delayed neutron fraction, which represents the proportion of neutrons released from fission processes that exhibit delayed emission, plays a crucial role in the reactor’s total neutron population, reactivity, and reactivity control systems. For VVER, the existing nuclear safety rules set a limit on the input rate of positive reactivity of $0.07 \beta_{eff}/s$, while the value of a “one-time” portion of reactivity should not exceed $0.3 \beta_{eff}$ (Ehst and Nuclear Engineering Division 2009).

In this work, the effects of IBA rods and enrichment of fuel on β_{eff} over the whole burnup process were studied. Serpent code calculates and provides the values of β_{eff} using different methods. For this work, only Meulekamp’s method (Meulekamp and Marck 2006) was used. In Fig. 8a, effect of fuel enrichment on β_{eff} is shown. As we know, higher fuel enrichment increases the probability of fission events and subsequently influences the number of delayed neutrons produced. Therefore, assemblies with 4.95 wt.% and 3.0 wt.% enriched fuel are studied for comparison. It is found that the higher enriched assembly has a higher value of β_{eff} of over the whole burnup process. For 3.0 wt.% and 4.95 wt.% enriched fuel assemblies, the difference of β_{eff} is

10.8% at 16 GWd/t burnup. Fig. 8b shows the effect of IBA rods on effective delayed neutron fraction. Here, the fuel assembly with 4.95 wt.% enrichment utilizing 30 IBAs, and that without any IBA were used to observe the effect of IBA on β_{eff} . Results show that IBA rods do not have any significant effect on β_{eff} . Hence, it can be deduced that the number of IBA rods used for suppression of early excess reactivity at BOC does not poses any reactor stability concern from the delayed neutron fraction perspective.

Temperature coefficients (TCs)

The temperature coefficients (TCs) are important because it aids in evaluating the built-in feedback mechanisms within a reactor. Negative TCs are always desirable, as they contribute to reactor safety. Tables 2, 3 shows the effects of IBA rods and fuel enrichment on the fuel temperature coefficient (FTC) and moderator temperature coefficient (MTC), respectively.

In this study, assemblies with maximum (4.95 wt.%) and minimum (2.0 wt) enriched fuel were analyzed. For FTC calculation, the nominal fuel temperature 873 K is increased to 1173K. The FTC at a given burnup is influenced by the presence of resonance-absorbing atoms such as U-238 and Pu-240. Therefore, higher fuel enrichment affects the neutron population and fission rate, which in turn impacts the FTC. Changes in enrichment also alter the thermal utilization factor, neutron absorption, and scattering behavior, all of which influence fuel temperature distribution and lead to a more negative FTC. As a result, the assembly with 2.0 wt.% enriched fuel exhibits FTC values that are 17.26% and 60.28% more negative than those of the 4.95 wt.% assembly at the BOL and 20 GWd/t respectively. However, at the EOL, the 4.95 wt.% enriched assembly shows a 30% more negative FTC compared to the 2.0 wt.% assembly. To understand the impact of IBA rods on FTC, fuel assembly of 4.95 wt.% enrichment has been

Figure 8. (a) Effect of enrichment of fuel on effective delayed neutron fraction. (b) Effect of IBA rods on effective delayed neutron fraction.

studied and found that IBA rods makes the FTC more negative. With burnup, the value of FTC becomes more negative especially at the EOL, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Effects of fuel enrichment and IBA rods on the fuel temperature coefficient (FTC)

Burnup (GWd/t)	FTC (pcm/°C) for 4.95 wt% enriched fuel		FTC (pcm/°C) for 2.0 wt% enriched fuel
	Without IBA rod	With 30 IBA rods	Without IBA rod
0	-2.782	-2.792	-3.262
20	-2.078	-3.073	-3.331
60	-2.847	-4.926	-1.992

Table 3 shows the MTC at BOL, 20 GWd/t and at EOL. For the MTC calculation, the nominal moderator temperature of 573 K was increased to 603 K. The MTC of low enriched fueled assembly is less negative than the high enriched assembly. The assembly with IBA rods has a less negative MTC at BOL and 20 GWd/t, however, at EOL, it becomes more negative, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Effects of fuel enrichment and IBA rods on the moderator temperature coefficient (MTC)

Burnup (GWd/t)	MTC (pcm/°C) for 4.95 wt% enriched fuel		MTC (pcm/°C) for 2.0 wt% enriched fuel
	Without IBA rod	With 30 IBA rods	Without IBA rod
0	-50.903269	-30.222870	-45.134363
20	-49.521186	-41.416442	-50.738764
60	-56.380353	-58.058963	-35.205430

Conclusions

The set of analysis of VVER-1200 reactor assemblies with varying enrichments (from 4.95 wt.% to 2.0 wt.%) has been studied for optimizing integrated burnable absorber

(IBA) and control rod (CR) effects as a way of managing early excess reactivity along with safety parameters. Higher enrichment results in higher infinite multiplication factor and increased excess reactivity, necessitating the use of additional IBA rods which is the mixture of fuel and 4% Gd₂O₃. The assembly with maximum enriched (4.95 wt.%) fuel required 30 IBA rods to reduce the k_{inf} from 1.32408 to 1.06983 at BOL. Conversely, assemblies with minimum enrichment (less than 2.5 wt.%) achieved a satisfactory performance without the use of IBA rods.

By inserting CRs more than 80% of assembly height, suppression of early excess reactivity can be accomplished effectively. At the BOL, withdrawing the CRs by 25 cm from full insertion reduces reactivity by over 15% for fuel with 4.95 wt.% enrichment. The CR worth decreases linearly with burnup. For 25, 75 and 125 cm withdraw of control rods, the CR worth are respectively 85.5, 32.7, and 7.2 pcm/cm at the BOL and 57.4, 23.1 and 4.9 pcm/cm at the EOL.

Fuel enrichment has a significant influence on the safety parameters: β_{eff} , FTC, and MTC. Higher enriched assemblies consistently show higher β_{eff} values throughout the burnup process. At a burnup of 16 GWd/t, the β_{eff} in 4.95 wt.% enriched fuel assembly is about 10.8% higher than that in 3.0 wt.% enriched fuel assembly. Regarding FTC, the assembly with 2.0 wt.% enriched fuel assembly shows values that are 17.26% and 60.28% more negative than those of the 4.95 wt.% assembly at the beginning of life (BOL) and at 20 GWd/t, respectively. However, by the EOL, the trend reverses, and the 4.95 wt.% assembly shows a 30% more negative FTC compared to the 2.0 wt.% assembly. The MTC of low enriched fueled assembly is less negative than the high enriched assembly. The uses of IBA rods make the FTC more negative, especially at the EOL, but their impact on β_{eff} and MTC is minimal.

In practical reactor operation, burnable absorbers are indeed not uniformly applied to every fuel assembly

and their distribution is optimized depending on the initial enrichment, power peaking constraints, burnup objectives, and specific core loading strategies. Therefore, further investigations will explore the combined effect of different enriched fuel assemblies on core behaviour, focusing on criticality, reloading processes, and safety parameters.

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